

Maduemezie Emeka Patrick

ABSTRACT

Abstract— Dr. Martens, owned by Griggs, is a UK-based footwear company that has transformed into a global brand synonymous with youth culture, creativity, and rebellion. The company's strategic branding through advertising, celebrity endorsements, and sustainability initiatives has significantly increased sales, surpassing £600 million as of March 2020. Dr. Martens has continually evolved its advertising methods to align with changing societal trends and subcultures, maintaining relevance across generations. Nigeria, as Africa's largest economy, presents a lucrative market for Dr. Martens to explore beyond its traditional markets. The growing interest in UK brands in Nigeria, coupled with the youthful demographic and vibrant urban culture, aligns perfectly with Dr. Martens' brand image, renowned for its connection to youth culture and defiance of societal norms. This paper evaluates potential growth areas, challenges in business operations, and estimates the market size for UK enterprises in Nigeria. Consequently, the Nigerian market offers a compelling opportunity for Dr. Martens to expand its international footprint and capitalize on the nation's economic growth trajectory.

Keywords: Dr. Martens, branding, youth culture, Nigeria, market expansion, footwear industry, globalization.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Dr. Martens with the ownership of Griggs, is a company in the UK that specializes in footwear. The company has undergone a transformation into a global brand that is closely aligned with young culture, creativity and rebellion. The company's adoption of its brand presence through advertisement, celebrity endorsements and a focus on sustainability growth has led to a significant increase in its sales to over 600 million pounds as of 2020 March. Dr Martens has kept on evolving in carrying out a method of advertising that aligns with a change in societal trends and subcultures, maintaining its relevance throughout generations up till this modern period (Wei, 2022).

Given its status as the largest economy in Africa, Nigeria offers a highly profitable market for Dr Martens to expand into, going beyond its usual markets. The Foreign and Commonwealth Office (FCO) commissioned a report from PwC which identified Nigeria as an excellent choice for UK businesses looking to expand into sectors other than oil and gas. The paper evaluates the areas with potential for growth, and the obstacles faced in conducting business, and calculates the estimated market size for UK enterprises in Nigeria (PwC, 2016).

By utilizing the information included in the research, Dr. Martens may strategically position itself to access Nigeria's rapidly growing consumer market, by matching its product offers with the preferences and current trends in the region. Moreover, Nigeria's large population of young people and dynamic urban culture make it a perfect match for Dr Martens' brand image, which is renowned for its connection to youth culture and defiance of societal norms. Hence, the Nigerian market presents a highly attractive prospect for Dr Martens to broaden its international presence and take advantage of the nation's upward economic trajectory.

* Maduemezie Emeka Patrick, is a graduate of Obafemi Awolowo University with a BA degree in philosophy. He is pursuing his research interests in business management, sustainability, human resource management, project management, international relations, ethics, and human rights advocacy. Correspondence should be sent to Athena Research. Email: xperiaresearch@gmail.com

© 2024 Maduemezie E. This is an open-access article which permits unrestricted use and distribution.

2.0 SWOT ANALYSIS OF INTERNAL AND EXTERNAL CONDITIONS

Both inherent and external factors of Dr Martens have a substantial impact. Conducting a SWOT analysis pointing out the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats gives a detailed background for developing strategic objectives and effectively navigating future possibilities. Dr Martens can stay ahead of other competitors and achieve sustainable growth by understanding its external market condition and internal capabilities. This allows the company to effectively use its strengths, eliminate its weaknesses, grab any opportunities and address any potential threats (Helms & Nixon, 2010). Embarking on this business strategy will allow the company to make adjustments to any change in customer preference, market trends and any industry problem while enhancing its strategic decision-making process.

Strength: Dr Martens excels in carrying out establishing a robust association with fashion, music and significant subcultures. Dr Martens emerges as a representation of philosophy and self-expression for several subculture groups such as mods, punks and grunge enthusiasts. This longstanding connection cultivates a devoted customer base and strengthens its brand attractiveness which spans from generation to generation (Prendergast, 2017). Furthermore, Dr Martens is highly known for its enduring fashion, and exceptional durability that appears to customers who are in search of enduring footwear that complements several style choices (Weresh, n.d). Dr Martens' continued success and consumer confidence can be attributed to its reputation for exceptional longevity and craftsmanship.

In addition, Dr Martens boasts a robust brand image that has enabled it to carry out maintenance in sales irrespective of implementing an increased change in the price of its products. The brand's iconic products, particularly its core boots have contributed to an increased volume of sales where price hacks have minimal impartation. Moreover, the company has pointed out their resilience in its direct-to-consumer (DTC) sales, which increased to more than 10 per cent across the globe making a representative half of the group revenue. The success of DTC channels is a reflection of the brand's strong connection with consumers as well as effective marketing strategies (Sutcliffe, 2023).

Weakness: Although Dr Martens possesses rigorous strength, it still has some drawbacks that have the potential to negatively impact its long-term expansion and durability. A significant challenge is the lack of clarity pertaining to the intended recipient of the message. Dr Martens lacks a well-defined target audience despite having several potential consumers. This makes it a challenge to efficiently customize a marketing strategy (Weresh, n.d). Furthermore, it is necessary for Dr Martens to be honest about its sustainability initiative implementation. This could potentially affect how the audience perceives and stays loyal to the brand. Dr. Martens, although afflicted with environmental protection organization had to embark on a well-defined sustainability measure in order to go on board with the changing demand of environmentally conscious consumers (Weresh, n.d).

Opportunities: Dr Martens has the potential to take advantage of several chances to enhance its competitive position in the change in demand pattern. An opportunity might be found while there is an increase in demand for sustainable brands. As a result of its growing environmental consciousness, people embark in the pursuit of products that are environmentally and ethically manufactured and sustainable. By bolstering its sustainability initiatives and successfully conveying them, without a doubt, Dr Martens can engage consumers who are environmentally conscious and distinguish itself from its competitors (Dr Martens, n.d). By incorporating a sustainable measure across its supply chain like reducing carbon emissions and procuring environmentally friendly materials, Dr Martens may not only foster enduring brand loyalty and enhance its reputation but also match itself with customers' value in the long run.

Moreover, Dr Marten can embark on the utilization of the experiential methods of advertisement to carry out an establishment of an immersive brand experience and cultivation of more profound ties with consumers. Events and pop-up shops provide chances for there to be direct contact, enabling customers to interact with the products firsthand and encounter the brand's

distinct personality and legacy. Through making a utilization of experimental marketing Dr. Martens may elicit emotional reactions, create excitement in the target audiences and cultivate brand loyalty. In addition, these events serve as an opportunity to promote brand narrative and share stories which will allow Dr. Martens to strengthen its genuineness, culture and principles. Furthermore, Dr Martens can increase its attractiveness and market presence while strategically collaborating with brand ambassadors and influencers who can engage a large number of audiences to patronize the company's product. Collaborating with influencers who are in the field of fashion and music will help increase brand visibility as they will establish a genuine connection with a large number of potential customers (Weresh, n.d).

Threats: Despite Dr Martens being the dominant position in the footwear business it is still comfortable with various threats that can negatively affect the success of the business. An eminent peril arises from the escalating rivalry posed by environmentally conscious businesses like Converse and Patagonia. Failure of Dr Martens to communicate its sustainability initiatives successfully could pose a threat to its market share since its competitors can be actively promoting sustainability and ethical practices (Weresh, n.d). In addition, as there is a change in consumer preference it might be a challenge for Dr Martens to remain relevant (Czarniewski, 2014).

<i>Strengths</i>	<i>Weaknesses</i>
Strong association with fashion, music, and subcultures	Lack of clarity on the target audience
Enduring fashion and exceptional durability	Lack of transparency in sustainability initiatives
Robust brand image and resilience in pricing strategies	
<i>Opportunities</i>	<i>Threats</i>
Increasing demand for sustainable brands	Rivalry from environmentally conscious competitors
Utilization of experiential marketing methods	Shifting cultural trends and consumer preferences

Table 1: The SWOT analysis table assesses Dr Martens's intrinsic strengths and weaknesses alongside extrinsic opportunities and threats.

3.0 PESTLE ANALYSIS ENTRY INTO THE NIGERIAN MARKET

In order to provide a thorough background into the sociological, political, economic, legal, environmental and technical aspects of Dr Martens's operation, performance and success in the Nigerian market, the PESTLE framework is needed as it looks into the external factors of the business.

Political Factors: Nigeria's political landscape is characterised by volatility and complexity with various problems like corruption (Essien, 2012). It is important for Dr Martens to pass

through the challenges of corruption which can be done by adhering to anti-corruption practice and making an engagement with government institutions in order to develop trust and ensure compliance with any regulations in the country. Additionally, political tensions and security risks can disrupt business activities, so it is vital to carry out strategic planning for risk management of the business (Ozili & Arun, 2020).

Economic Factor: Nigeria is known as the most populous country in Africa which gives favourable prospects for Dr Martens to have a high increase in sales in the country. However, Nigeria suffers economic challenges such as an increase in inflation rate and currency volatility which consequently lead to a hike in the price of goods. (Central Bank of Nigeria, 2022). Variations in Gross Domestic Product (GDP) growth, steady rise in inflation and volatility of exchange rate all have a direct impact on the consumer capability to purchase footwear products. It is necessary for Dr Martens to make a critical analysis to carry out cost control and adopt strategic pricing in order for them to keep on maintaining their profitability irrespective of the economic challenges the country is facing.

Sociological Factor: Understanding Nigerian consumer lifestyle choices, demographic trends and cultural values is essential for Dr. Martens to tailor its marketing strategies and products it offers to the consumers effectively. Nigeria's diverse population dynamics and cultural variety impact the kind of products consumers prefer and their purchasing patterns (The Strategy Story, 2022). Through customizing prompts as well as marketing messaging to align with domestic cultural preferences, Dr Martens can increase its market reach targeted to certain groups of people across different regions within Nigeria.

Technological Factor: Dr Martens' operations and marketing strategies are greatly impacted by the Nigerian technological landscape, which is marked by infrastructural issues and digital advancements (Ventures Africa, n.d.). While urban locations could have more developed infrastructure, rural areas however frequently do not have reliable internet and energy, which makes production and distribution difficult. To effectively engage with Nigerian consumers, Dr Martens needs to invest in creative technologies and tailor digital marketing techniques (Euromonitor International, 2021).

Environment Factor: Sustainable techniques in the footwear sector are required due to rising consumer environmental awareness and strict restrictions on waste management and pollution control (Rahman, n.d). To appeal to Nigerian customers who care about the environment, Dr. Martens should prioritize sustainability projects including employing eco-friendly materials, cutting carbon emissions, and putting ethical manufacturing procedures into place. By integrating environmental best practices into its business operations, the company may boost its brand recognition and obtain a competitive edge in the Nigerian market.

Legal Factor: Adhering to the strict legal regulations of Nigeria and the protection law of consumers is necessary for Dr Martens to mitigate risks and maintain its reputation as a responsible business (Oyebo, 2023). Compliance with regulations in relation to competition laws, quality control and health standards is important in order to prevent any legal conflicts, and reputational damage and avoid fines. By carrying out ethical business practices and strong compliance processes, Dr Martens can uphold its corporate image and build the trust that Nigerian consumers will have in them (Federal Competition, 2023).

<i>Factor</i>	<i>Impact on Dr Martens in Nigeria</i>
<i>Political</i>	Complexity and volatility require adherence to anti-corruption practices, engagement with government, and strategic risk management.
<i>Economic</i>	A large population offers sales potential, but inflation, currency

	volatility, and GDP changes affect purchasing power, necessitating cost control and strategic pricing efforts.
<i>Sociological</i>	Understanding consumer lifestyle, demographics, and cultural values is crucial for tailored marketing strategies to reach diverse consumer groups across regions.
<i>Technological</i>	Infrastructural issues and digital advancements affect operations and marketing, requiring investment in creative technologies and tailored digital marketing techniques.
<i>Legal</i>	Adherence to competitive law, consumer protection law, legal regulation and quality control is crucial in upholding an accountable corporate image and mitigating any risk that comes across to the organization.
<i>Environment</i>	Rising environmental awareness necessitates sustainable practices, including eco-friendly materials and ethical manufacturing, to appeal to environmentally conscious consumers.

Table 2: The table shows the PESTLE analysis for Dr. Martens coming into the Nigerian market

4.0 STRATEGIC RECOMMENDATIONS: A SWOT AND PESTLE ANALYSIS PERSPECTIVE

The SWOT analysis performed on Dr Martens identifies significant internal and external elements that influence the company's strategic trajectory. Dr. Martens excels in its robust brand image that is firmly established within several subcultures including mods, punks, and grunge aficionados, resulting in a devoted consumer base spanning many generations (Prendergast, 2017). The brand's long-lasting style and extraordinary resilience further strengthen its position in the footwear market, leading to consistent sales even in the face of price fluctuations (Sutcliffe, 2023). Nonetheless, the absence of a clearly identified target audience presents a notable obstacle, impeding the ability to tailor marketing tactics and sustainability activities (Weresh, n.d). In addition, the company is confronted with competition from environmentally aware rivals such as Converse and Patagonia. This emphasizes the importance of properly conveying its sustainability initiatives in order to retain its market position.

However, the PESTLE analysis gives an overview of the extrinsic factors which could consequently influence Dr Martens's aptitude to come into the Nigerian market. The political environment in Nigeria is marked by corruption and regulatory ambiguity, which presents obstacles that necessitate the company's compliance with anti-corruption measures and active involvement with government institutions (Essien, 2012). The economic variables of inflation and

currency volatility in Nigeria might impact the purchasing power of consumers and their desire for high-end footwear items. This situation calls attention to implementing strategic pricing and cost management measures (Obstfeld et. al, 2020).

The preferences of the consumers and their purchasing behaviours are influenced by social dynamics like demographic trends and cultural relevance. This points out the essentiality of delivering the products and carrying out business techniques that are customized specifically to these factors (Ventures Africa, n.d). In addition, the infrastructure of technology difficulties poses major challenges in the manufacturing and distribution process, which necessitate an incentive solution and tailored digital strategies (Euromonitor International, 2021). Furthermore, it is essential to adhere to the consumer protection law, and quality control in order to prevent Dr Martens's reputation from being tarnished and establish trust among the consumers (Oyebo, 2023).

Dr Martens can exploit the opportunities which can be found in the assessment to improve its competitive position. To engage clients who are environmentally conscious in Nigeria, the company should make sustainability measures a priority (Weresh, n.d). Adapting marketing messages and products to match the specifications of cultural preferences within a particular locality in Nigeria can increase the attractiveness of Dr Martens among consumers in the Nigerian market (Weresh, n.d). Furthermore, carrying out an engagement in cutting-edge solutions is important in order to battle the issues of technological infrastructure and guarantee abiding by the rules and regulations to ensure smooth operation in the Nigerian market without any negative consequences (Federal Competition, 2023).

5.0 STRATEGIC SEGMENTATION, TARGETING, AND POSITIONING: BLUEPRINT FOR SUCCESS IN NIGERIA

Segmentation, targeting, and positioning (STP) are the foundation of carrying out a marketing strategy in business (Ezenwa, 2018). Through this marketing strategy, Dr Martens could penetrate and excel in the Nigerian market. Market segmentation is an important marketing concept that has to do with the segment of the market which are psychological behavioural and geographic aspects. It will be an advantage to divide the market based on the lifestyle and cultural influences for Dr Martens to expand in the Nigerian market. Nigeria's segment entails various young people located in the urban areas who are influential in the setting of music aficionados, and fashion trends who prioritize the search for unique footwear that is long-lasting (Alao, et al, 2016).

Targeting in marketing can be said to be a process of picking certain market groups carefully in line with the objective of the company and the resources available (Wrike, n.d). Dr Martens being a company known for its rebellious and enduring image, should concentrate its targeting efforts on young consumers living in urban locations who are passionate about fashion, and music aficionados. Dr Martens improved its relevance and attractiveness in the Nigerian market while customizing marketing methods and offering products which align with the preferences of these segments.

Positioning deals with the capability to shape not just the perceptions of the consumers but also their attitudes in the context of the market sector (Corporate Finance Institution, n.d). Within Nigeria's dynamic fashion industry, Dr. Martens has the potential to establish a distinct position not only as a type of footwear, but also as an emblem of defiance, uniqueness, and enduring fashion. Dr Martens sets itself apart from both local and international competition in the footwear market by emphasizing its extensive tradition, exceptional craftsmanship, and famous designs. The raw yet sophisticated appearance of the product appeals to Nigerians who want to showcase their distinct personalities and question traditional standards.

In addition, Dr Marten's adaptability is highlighted based on its capacity to shift from casual wear on a daily base to a fashionable festival look effectively, making it appealing to several Nigerians. Dr Martens is not just about fashion but also about cultural symbols of self-expression

whether one is enjoying the vibrant beats of Afrobeat at a music festival or making an exploration in busy areas like Lagos (Admin 2022).

In the midst of Nigeria's emergence as a prominent fashion centre, Dr Martens has the opportunity to establish itself as a highly desirable brand that goes beyond passing trends. By providing individuals with the ability to distinguish themselves while being authentic, Dr. Martens can solidify its place in the market (Admin 2022). By carrying out this, it is not only becoming a crucial component of Nigeria's fashion story but also acquiring a portion of the market, showcasing the nation's steadfast and vibrant energy dedicated to uniqueness.

Dr. Martens coming into a new market like Nigeria necessitates a deep analysis of social, economic and cultural variables. Therefore, it is crucial for Dr Martens to carry out marketing research to gain insight into tastes, cultural subtleties of Nigerian consumers and purchasing patterns. This understanding will guide its segmentation, targeting, and positioning tactics, guaranteeing that they connect with the local market.

6.0 APPLYING THE 7PS FRAMEWORK

In order for Dr Martens to succeed in the Nigerian market the 7ps marketing mix strategy should be put in place which encompasses product, price, place, promotion, process, people and physical evidence.

Fig 1: 7ps Marketing Mix (Zahra, 2019)

Firstly, in terms of products, Dr. Martens must ensure that it offers products that align with what Nigerian customers prefer or need emphasizing localization, quality and innovation to cater to local tastes (Onah, 2022). By adapting and comprehending the unique demand of the Nigerian market, Dr Martens can enhance product appeal.

Secondly, in terms of pricing, it is crucial for Dr Martens to navigate the economic challenges and heightened price sensitivity prevailing in Nigeria by carrying out an implementation of the strategies of competitive pricing. Dr Martens must strike a balance between profitability and affordability, given the downturn in the economy and consumer propensity to prioritize saving over spending as a result of low confidentiality levels (Onyekwelu, 2021).

Thirdly, based on place, Dr Martens should concentrate on its distribution efforts in populated

areas like Lagos, Abuja and Port Harcourt. Also, the proximate close to university areas where there are tons number of youth population (Onah, 2022).

Moreover, Dr Martens should adopt a promotional marketing campaign in order to not just raise awareness of the company product but also drive traffic while engaging the consumer. Based on the targeted location an advertisement can be made (Samuel, n.d). For example, for Nigeria to be aware of a particular product a social media advertisement can be created while choosing the location as Nigeria.

The people aspect underscores highly trained staff who embody the brand's values. Investing in the incentives and the training of staff will ensure the overall success of the organization, as the company produce an outstanding staff that can give exceptional services to the customers (Dr Martens, 2023).

Furthermore, Dr Martens' marketing process should implement sustainability with a clear agenda while operating its activities in Nigeria. This entails strategic planning, effective communication and stakeholder engagement at board and operational levels. By implementing sustainability into Dr Marten's process business, the company will be able to appeal to socially conscious consumers and increase its brand reputation not just in Nigeria but the entire world (Dr Martens, 2023).

Finally, the physical evidence entails immersive retail experiences that point out the product range and the brand heritage of Dr. Martens. Testimonies and customer reviews further reinforce trustworthiness and brand credibility within the Nigerian market (Dr Martens, 2023).

7.0 CONCLUSION

Dr Martens's SWOT and PESTEL analysis provides a deep comprehensive of both intrinsic and external elements that impact the business direction strategically, specifically in relationship to the expansion in the Nigerian market. Dr Marten excels in terms of strong brand presence, long-lasting fashion appeal, and direct-to-consumer sales techniques. However, difficulties arise for Dr Martens due to the requirement for transparency in sustainability projects and difficulties in accurately identifying the specific audience. Furthermore, the study shows a potential advantage in the dynamic market for immersive marketing experiences as well as a brand that is eco-friendly, while potential disadvantages include a change in demand pattern and intense competitors.

This research influences Dr Martens to implement some marketing strategies and approaches. One of these is the prioritization of sustainability initiatives, which can set the business apart. Furthermore, it is crucial to implement a technique that aligns with the cultural preferences of Nigerian consumers in order to develop a strong presence and penetration of the market within the country. Furthermore, it is important to tackle the technological issues to ensure a smooth manufacturing production process. Following the consumer protection law and regulatory bodies it is necessary to make the development of confidence or trust among Nigerian consumers.

Moreover, in order to develop a robust presence in a new market like Nigeria STP must be put in place. Dr Marten improved its importance and attractiveness in the market while identifying and targeting a particular marketing segment. Implementing the 7ps marketing mix is another addition. This marketing mix will ensure that the product is aligned with local preferences, is distributed strategically, priced competitively, and the company is staffed with skilled employees and is run effectively, also ensures the business provides appealing physical retail experiences. adopting a comprehensive strategy that incorporates these observations and suggestions will allow Dr Martens to effectively perform well in the Nigerian market and attain long-lasting expansion and brand triumph.

8.0 RECOMMENDATIONS

There are many recommendations for the progress of Dr. Martens while entering the Nigerian market. However, the suggested few include the following:

1. Market research should be conducted in order to the particular target audience in Nigeria accurately (Weresh, n.d). This research should entail the examination of demographic profiling, cultural insights, and customer behaviour analysis in order to customize marketing strategies effectively (Alao et al., 2016).

2. Make sustainability activities a priority in the market strategy in Nigeria (Weresh, n.d). With the increasing consciousness of the environment among consumers across the globe, including Nigeria, (Rahman, n.d), Dr Martens has a high tendency to differentiate itself from the rest of its rivals by implementing sustainability best practices such as lessening carbon footprint by making use of eco-friendly materials that can less pollute the environment (Weresh, n.d).

3. Utilize experiential marketing strategies to make the development of engaging brand experiences among Nigerian consumers (Alao et al., 2016). Events, temporary retail spaces, and partnerships with influential individuals in the local community can promote direct interaction and cultivate emotional bonds with the brand (Weresh, n.d). Implementing such measures would not only strengthen customer loyalty but also intensify Dr Martens' influence and impact in the Nigerian market.

4. Modify product offerings, pricing strategies, and distribution methods to align with the specific local environment and economic conditions in Nigeria (Central Bank of Nigeria, 2022). This may involve providing product variations tailored to certain regions, adopting competitive pricing tactics, and strategically positioning retail stores in busy locations (Onah, 2022).

- 5 Ensure compliance with legal norms and uphold ethical business practices in order to create and sustain a reputation in the Nigerian market (Oyebo, 2023). Adhering to quality standards, consumer protection legislation, and anti-corruption measures is crucial for establishing confidence and reducing operating risks (Essien, 2012).

These recommendations will enhance Dr Martens's competitive advantage, sustainability and flexibility in the Nigerian market, which will consequently bring about the company expansion and drive them toward success.

REFERENCES

- [1] Admin. (2022). Segmentation & targeting in Nigeria I. WOW. <https://woweffect.com.ng/marketing/segmentation-targeting-nigeria/>
- [2] Alao, A. E., Egwuonwu, T. K., & Adeeko, A. L. (2016). Niche Marketing and Value-Based Differentiation in the Footwear Industrial Sub-Sector in Nigeria. *International Journal of Business and Management Invention*, 5(3), 18-26. Retrieved from [https://www.ijbmi.org/papers/Vol\(5\)3/Version-2/C50302018026.pdf](https://www.ijbmi.org/papers/Vol(5)3/Version-2/C50302018026.pdf)
- [3] Central Bank of Nigeria. (2022). February Economic Report 2022 [PDF document]. Retrieved from <https://www.cbn.gov.ng/Out/2022/RSD/February%2520Economic%2520Report%25202022A.pdf>
- [4] Corporate Finance Institute. (n.d.). Market Positioning. Retrieved from <https://corporatefinanceinstitute.com/resources/management/market-positioning/>
- [5] Czarniewski, S. (2014). Changes in consumer behaviour in the market and the value of companies. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Management Sciences*, 2(2), 61. <https://www.idpublications.org/wp-content/uploads/2014/09/CHANGES-IN-CONSUMER-BEHAVIOUR-IN-THE-MARKET-AND-THE-VALUE-OF-COMPANIES.pdf>
- [6] Dr Martens PLC annual report (2023) https://www.drmartensplc.com/application/files/8316/8624/2435/Dr._Martens_plc_Annual_Report_2023.pdf
- [7] Dr. Martens. (n.d.). *Sustainability*. Retrieved from <https://www.drmartensplc.com/sustainability/>
- [8] Essien, E. B. (2012). Corruption and Economic Development in Nigeria: A Materialistic Observation. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 3(14), 34. Retrieved from <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/234645776.pdf>
- [9] Euromonitor International. (2021). Consumer Lifestyles in Nigeria. Retrieved from <https://www.euromonitor.com/consumer-lifestyles-in-nigeria/report>
- [10] Ezenwa, J. (2020). Positioning and objective. LinkedIn. https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/positioning-objective-joseph-ezenwa?trk=articles_directory
- [11] Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Commission (FCCPC). (2023). Potential Anti-Competitive Conduct in Association of POS Operators: Statement of Setting Prices for Services. Retrieved from <https://fccpc.gov.ng/update-on-potential-anti-competitive-conduct-in-association-of-pos-operators-statement-of-setting-prices-for-services/>
- [12] Helms, M. M., & Nixon, J. (2010). Exploring SWOT analysis – where are we now? A review of academic research from the last decade. *Journal of Strategy and Management*, 3(3), 215-251. [Available at: <https://members.bestbusinesscoach.ca/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/Exploring-SWOT-analysis-%E2%80%93-where-are-we-now-A-review-of-academic-research-from-the-last-decade-2.pdf>]
- [13] Larsen, N. (2010). *Market Segmentation: A framework for determining the right target customers* (Bachelor's thesis). Aarhus School of Business. https://abm.report/Resources/Whitepapers/17aa6df1-a36a-45ab-9249-f64c68bc70b1_BA.pdf
- [14] Obstfeld, M., & Rogoff, K. (2020). Exchange Rate Dynamics Redux. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 135(1), 1-58. <https://www.journals.uchicago.edu/doi/10.1086/261997>
- [15] Onah, O (2022). The best locations for setting up a business in Nigeria. SmartSMSolutions. <https://smartsmsolutions.com/blog/118-sms-marketing/small-business/1730-the-best-locations-for-setting-up-a-business-in-nigeria>
- [16] Onyekwelu, S. (n.d.). Nigerians want affordable prices but Premium Products - Uzo - Businessday Ng. Business Day. <https://www.google.com/amp/s/businessday.ng/interview/article/nigerians-want-affordable-prices-but-premium-products-uzo/%3famp=1?espv=1>
- [17] Oyebo, O. (2023). Taxation and Regulatory Compliance in Nigeria: Navigating the Legal Landscape. [LinkedIn article]. Retrieved from https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/taxation-regulatory-compliance-nigeria-navigating-legal-oyebo?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_android&utm_campaign=share_via
- [18] Ozili, P. K., & Arun, T. (2020). Spillover of COVID-19: Impact on the Global Economy. *Journal of Economic Structures*, 9(1), 1-13. Retrieved from https://papers.ssm.com/sol3/Delivery.cfm/SSRN_ID4280893_code1996195.pdf?abstractid=3562570&mirid=1&type=2
- [19] Prendergast, A. (2017). How Dr. Martens became iconic. Retrieved March 19, 2022, from <https://therake.com/stories/style/how-dr-martens-became-iconic/>
- [20] PwC. (2016, March). Seizing the opportunity: An economic assessment of key sectors of opportunity for

UK businesses in Nigeria. Retrieved from <https://www.pwc.com/ng/en/assets/pdf/uk-trade-investment-in-nigeria.pdf>

- [21] Rahman, M. (2023). PESTEL analysis of the Footwear Industry. www.howandwhat.net.
<https://www.howandwhat.net/pestel-analysis-footwear-industry/>
- [22] Robson, M. J., & Horn, S. (2022). Marketing strategies. *International Business*.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/hebz/9780198861898.003.0014>
- [23] Samuel, A. M., (2023, November 28). Types of advertising in Nigeria. LED SCREEN & OUT-of- HOME ADVERTISING - BLOG. <https://viradsmedia.wordpress.com/2019/06/25/types-of-advertising-understanding-the-types-of-advertising-in-nigeria/>
- [24] Stiefenhofer, P. (2021). Towards understanding prices and ethics: Ethical consumers with price-dependent utilities. *Theoretical Economics Letters*, 11(03). <https://doi.org/10.4236/tel.2021.113031>
- [25] Sutcliffe, C. (2023). Dr Martens credits brand strength for price hikes having ‘limited impact’ on sales. Marketing Week. Retrieved from <https://www.marketingweek.com/dr-martens-price-impact-sales/>
- [26] The Strategy Story. (2022). Unilever PESTEL Analysis. Retrieved from <https://thestrategystory.com/blog/unilever-pestel-analysis/>
- [27] Ventures Africa. (n.d.). Unilever Nigeria Plc makes 51 per cent profit despite a challenging 2023. Retrieved from <https://venturesafrica.com/unilever-nigeria-plc-makes-51-per-cent-profit-despite-a-challenging-2023/#:~:text=Larger%20corporations%2C%20including%20Unilever%20Nigeria,infrastructure%2C%20and%20unfavourable%20government%20policies.>
- [28] Wei, A. (2022). Study on the historical changes of Dr Martens Martin Boots Advertisement. Proceedings of the 2022 International Conference on Science Education and Art Appreciation (SEAA 2022), 410–416. https://doi.org/10.2991/978-2-494069-05-3_51
- [29] Weresh, S. (n.d.). DR. MARTENS [Creative project]. Retrieved from <https://scholarsbank.uoregon.edu/xmlui/bitstream/handle/1794/23950/Final%2520Thesis-Weresh%2520%2528Booklet%2529.pdf?sequence=2&isAllowed=y>
- [30] Wrike. (n.d.). What Is Targeting in Marketing? Retrieved from <https://www.wrike.com/marketing-guide/faq/what-is-targeting-in-marketing/>
- [31] Zahra., Z. (2019). What are the 7ps of marketing mix and how should it be used? LinkedIn. <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/what-7ps-marketing-mix-how-should-used-zahra-zahedi>